

Multi-User QoE Optimization in Virtual Reality Gaming using RL on Mobile Edge Networks

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Abstract

In this paper, we explore delivering mobile edge Virtual Reality (VR) gaming services with comprehensive and satisfactory Quality of Experience (QoE) across a distributed edge network. Our goal is to meet the QoE needs of all users, addressing both latency and visual considerations. We systematically capture the unique attributes of mobile VR games, including numerous independent objects with distinct rendering pipelines, diverse rendering levels, tight end-to-end delay requirements, and high bandwidth usage. We demonstrate that this challenge can be formulated as a Mixed-Integer Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Programming (MIQCQP) problem. By leveraging reinforcement learning techniques, we introduce a flexible and adaptive QoE weight formulation that incorporates symbolic generalization and real-time feedback loops. Unlike existing studies that often focus on single-user scenarios, our paper comprehensively addresses visual and latency concerns across multiple users. We employ optimization techniques through eigenvalue analysis and Lagrange-constrained methods, providing a scalable and robust framework for dynamically adjusting QoE weights based on user interactions and environmental factors. This approach enables us to deliver QoE-centric edge-assisted mobile VR gaming services to a large user base, advancing beyond current limitations in the field.

Keywords: Visualization, Multi-access edge computing, Bandwidth, Virtual reality, Games, Quality of service, Quality of experience, Mobile Edge Computing, Resource management, Servers, Standards, QoE, VR, QoS, MEC, XR

1 Introduction

In recent years, Virtual Reality (VR) technology has witnessed remarkable advancements, offering users immersive and interactive experiences within virtual environments. This surge in popularity has spurred the widespread adoption of VR-assisted services and applications, delivering significantly more engaging and immersive visual experiences compared to traditional 2D video formats [1, 2].

To provide a satisfying user experience, VR systems must address two critical criteria [3–5]: minimizing interactive latency and delivering high-fidelity visual rendering. Ensuring minimal latency enhances system responsiveness, thereby reducing potential dizziness or discomfort among users, while meeting high-quality visual standards heightens the immersive nature of the VR experience.

As an emerging solution, edge-assisted mobile VR leverages the computational resources of edge cloudlets to enhance the Quality of Experience (QoE) for users [3, 6–10]. This approach addresses the increasing demand for seamless and immersive VR environments. For instance, studies such as [8, 9] explore rendering the entire frame on edge devices, while [10] investigates the feasibility of achieving high-quality mobile VR. Additionally, [7] incorporates considerations for Field of View (FoV) and saliency during frame rendering. However, these studies focus primarily on isolated scenarios rather than offering a holistic approach to multi-user environments.

Fig. 1 An illustrative overview showcasing the intricate network and computing infrastructure of a distributed edge-assisted mobile VR gaming system, highlighting its components, connectivity, and interactions.

Within the realm of VR 360-degree video streaming services, research efforts have concentrated on mobile-oriented platforms [6, 7, 11–13]. These platforms often involve pre-rendering and caching panoramic content at the edge to provide smoother streaming experiences for mobile users. While these studies provide valuable insights into mobile 360-degree video streaming systems, they do not directly address the unique challenges of mobile VR gaming. This distinction arises due to differences in user behavior, interaction dynamics, and system requirements. The design considerations for reducing data transmission rates and improving user experience must therefore be tailored specifically to mobile VR gaming scenarios.

Figure 1 visually represents a distributed edge-assisted mobile VR gaming system. In this setup, VR games are deployed across multiple edge devices by the provider to support various users. Unlike focusing solely on individual user experience, the emphasis lies in optimizing the collective Quality of Experience (QoE) for all users. The central challenge is to devise a service provisioning strategy that allocates rendering computation and resource distribution effectively within the constraints of edge computing resources.

This work investigates the challenge of delivering high-quality mobile edge VR gaming services within a distributed edge network. Our objective is to meet the QoE needs of users, balancing latency and visual fidelity, while introducing a reinforcement learning-based approach to enable real-time adaptability. The unique characteristics of edge-assisted mobile VR gaming introduce distinct challenges:

1. **Numerous Independent Objects:** Modern VR gaming environments, such as those featuring avatars or weapons, incorporate independent rendering pipelines for each object. This significantly expands the search space for placement decisions and complicates optimization.
2. **Diverse Rendering Levels:** VR/3D games offer multiple rendering options to cater to varying QoE requirements. Selecting optimal rendering levels adds complexity to decision-making.
3. **Tight End-to-End Delay Requirements:** Mobile VR games demand stringent end-to-end delay constraints, typically below 15 milliseconds. This delay includes rendering, encoding, and transmission time (Figure 2), making traditional linear programming frameworks unsuitable.
4. **High Bandwidth Usage:** The visual demands of mobile VR games result in high bandwidth consumption, which directly affects rendering levels and delay. Balancing these conflicting QoE requirements is critical in edge-assisted VR gaming systems.
5. **Dynamic and Adaptive Resource Management:** To address the dynamic nature of user interactions and network conditions, reinforcement learning (RL) is employed. RL enables the system to learn optimal policies for resource allocation and rendering decisions by iteratively interacting with the environment and adapting to changes in real time.

In this paper, we explore the delivery of high-quality mobile edge VR gaming services across a distributed network. We address these unique challenges by integrating QoE optimization, advanced weight selection techniques, and reinforcement

Fig. 2 Latencies observed in mobile VR gaming with support from edge computing, illustrating the time delays between user interactions and corresponding responses within the virtual environment.

learning into a comprehensive framework. The problem is formulated as a Mixed Integer Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Programming (MIQCQP) model, focusing on meeting QoE needs while considering both latency and visual aspects. This work builds upon our previous research, which focused on static resource allocation for optimizing QoE in VR systems using traditional optimization methods [14].

2 Related Work

There is a growing body of literature on optimizing Quality of Experience (QoE) in virtual reality (VR) environments, focusing on video transmission, machine learning-based QoE predictions, and optimization techniques. Prior research has addressed various challenges, but gaps remain in user-centric testing, dynamic feedback integration, and real-world adaptation, which are tackled in this paper.

QoE evaluation for VR video transmission has been explored in numerous studies. For instance, the impact of video transmission impairments on user experience was investigated for 360-degree VR video streaming in [15]. While this study provides insights into user perception, it does not fully account for the role of network latency in dynamic environments. Similarly, [16] studies the application of massive MIMO technology for 360-degree VR video transmission to improve QoE but overlooks the effects of user mobility and changing bandwidth demands during VR experiences.

Machine learning-based QoE prediction has also been extensively studied. In [17], a deep learning framework was proposed to predict QoE for VR applications over Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN). While this model effectively predicts QoE under specific conditions, it does not consider variability in user behavior or device heterogeneity. Subjective QoE metrics integrated with machine learning were studied in [18], where prediction models were used to match user ratings. However, this work

does not address key environmental factors such as lighting conditions and background noise, which can significantly influence user experience in real-world settings.

Optimization techniques for VR QoE have been a major focus of recent research. Reinforcement learning (RL)-based frameworks have been proposed in [19] for optimizing VR streaming QoE in digital twin-enabled multi-access edge computing (MEC) environments. However, these solutions often fail to adapt effectively to real-world user behaviors over extended periods. Similarly, [20] explores the use of Multi-Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) in terahertz wireless networks to enhance VR QoE. Although the study provides valuable insights into network-assisted QoE improvements, it lacks user-centric testing under diverse network conditions and geographic mobility patterns. Additionally, [21] investigates attention-based QoE-aware digital twin strategies empowered by edge computing to optimize resource allocation for immersive multi-user VR sessions. While this study offers insights into QoE improvements by leveraging edge computing and dynamic resource distribution, it does not fully address variations in user behavior across different interaction styles.

Adaptive streaming techniques for VR content have been extensively studied to ensure QoE under varying network conditions. For instance, [22] explores machine learning approaches to predict QoE for immersive VR streaming, using encrypted QoS features to optimize adaptive streaming decisions. Although this method significantly improves QoE during streaming sessions, it does not fully address the impact of sudden latency spikes or environmental disruptions. Additionally, reinforcement learning-based strategies have been employed to optimize QoE in digital twin-empowered MEC frameworks, which dynamically allocate resources to reduce latency and improve user satisfaction during VR sessions. However, while these methods show promise, they do not fully address rapid changes in user behavior and device heterogeneity in real-world settings [23]. Despite significant advancements, further work is required to integrate these methods with adaptive feedback loops to better handle unpredictable conditions in VR environments.

Similar to the present study, prior work has sought to address QoE challenges under diverse constraints. However, this paper advances the state of the art by introducing a flexible and adaptive QoE weight formulation that incorporates symbolic generalization, real-time feedback loops, and optimization through eigenvalue analysis and Lagrange-constrained techniques. This framework dynamically adjusts QoE weights based on user interaction and environmental factors, providing a scalable and robust approach for VR applications.

3 System Model

3.1 Problem Definition

Let's examine a distributed edge system, where the collection of edges is represented by $\mathcal{D} := \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$. An expression is given $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, this ensures that each decision d encompasses both local edge and distributed placement possibilities, offering flexibility in object allocation strategies for user i 's object j . The variable d represents the decision for placing an object, which can either be take values from the set $\{0\}$ for local execution edge or chosen from the set \mathcal{D} representing alternative placement

options in distributed edge clouds. The edge servers or access points are co-located with the first network gateways (such as WiFi access points and 4G/5G base stations) of the end users. It is assumed that the Virtual Reality (VR) game has been deployed both on the edges and on the mobile devices. The set of mobile VR game users is denoted as $\mathcal{I} := \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$. The set of objects within the viewpoint of user i 's is represented as \mathcal{J}_i . The VR game offers various rendering levels for each object, and the collection of these available rendering levels is indicated by $\mathcal{L} := \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$.

3.2 Modeling the Binary Variable

We define $x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$ as a binary variable, where $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, and $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$. It represents the decision regarding the placement of object j for user i . When $d = 0$, it indicates local execution. Therefore, if $x_{i,j,d} = 1$, it denotes that object j for user i is displayed on edge d , while $x_{i,j,d} = 0$ implies that object j for user i is not displayed on edge d when $d \in \mathcal{D}$. Similarly, $x_{i,j,0} = 1$ suggests that object j for user i is displayed locally edge, whereas $x_{i,j,0} = 0$ implies otherwise. The binary variable $x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether is utilized in the d^{th} position. If $x_{i,j,d} = 1$, it denotes that it is employed in the d^{th} position, while $x_{i,j,d} = 0$ implies otherwise. For $x_{i,j,d}$, these binary variables are used to model the connection constraint for each object j within user i 's panorama to precisely connect to the edge. Therefore, the connection constraint is:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (1)$$

This constraint ensures that for each object j within the user i 's panorama view, the sum of the binary variables $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ over all bitrate levels d (including level 0) is equal to 1. This implies that exactly one bitrate level is chosen for the uplink transmission for each object in the panorama.

3.3 Modeling the QoE Objective

The users' QoE in visual panorama experiences depends on the perceived importance of objects, denoted by $w_{i,j}$ for user i and object j . We assume $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} = 1$. We adopt a linear QoE model for bitrate [7, 11, 12, 24], suitable for high-bitrate mobile VR gaming, approximating more complex models like logarithmic and PSNR/SSIM. Previous studies used bitrates from 8Mbps to 48Mbps [25], fixed at 36Mbps [26], and 8Mbps to 32Mbps in our study. Our findings show that the linear model adequately approximates complex QoE models with errors below 5.8% for logarithmic and 2.6% for PSNR. Given μ as the bitrate for rendering level 1, the expected QoE for user i , as specified in [27], can be defined as follows:

$$QoE_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} \cdot q(\mu, l_{i,j}), \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (2)$$

where the function $q()$ is a mapping function, which maps the bitrate to the quality perceived by the user. $l_{i,j}$ the rendering level for object j of user i and $w_{i,j}$ the visual QoE weight or object j of user i . In the context of VR, "rendering level" typically refers to the quality and complexity of the graphical rendering or graphics rendering

of the virtual environment. Rendering is the process of generating the images that users see in the VR headset, and the rendering level is a measure of the visual fidelity and detail in those images.

3.4 Rendering and Encoding Delay Constraint

In the context of VR gaming, rendering involves the generation of a digital image that can be displayed on the screen. This process relies on 3D models and various rendering parameters such as lighting, materials, textures, and rendering complexity. Our experiments demonstrate a direct correlation between rendering and encoding time and rendering complexity. This observation aligns with similar experiments conducted in [28, 29], which indicate that rendering and encoding time exhibit a linear relationship with rendering precision. Consequently, we represent rendering and encoding time as a linear function of rendering complexity. The interaction among objects is represented by the ‘dilation factor’, as mentioned in [30]. According to [30], the extension of computational speed is directly proportional to the workload, where the workload is defined as the number of objects in our specific context. We use $\alpha_{d,1}$, $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$ to denote the dilation factor.

Consider $h_{i,j,d}$ as the combined rendering and encoding time for object j of user i at location d , where $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, and there is no contention in terms of CPU cycles. Consequently, the rendering time for object j of user i at location d , where $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, can be expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d}. \quad (3)$$

Note that $h_{i,j,d}$ describes the computational time for a virtual object for a user at a specific location within a virtual or augmented reality context, rather than explicitly referring to a camera.

3.5 Transmission Delay Constraint

The exchange of data between the edge and the mobile device is crucial for rendering objects on the edge side. This data exchange is termed as transmission delay, which comprises two key components: the time taken for the mobile device to upload data to the edge (uploading time) and the time for the edge to send back rendered data to the mobile device (downloading time). Each component consists of two parts: the time required for data transmission (sending time) and the time taken for data to travel from one end to the other (propagation time) [8–10].

Sending Time: The superficial area, which represents the visible surface area, of object j for user i is denoted as $s_{i,j}$. In the context of this study, the resolution ratio of an object refers to the number of pixels per unit area and per frame level after rendering, denoted by $r_{i,j}$ for object j belonging to user i , while q_i denotes the frame rate of user i . The bitrate per pixel of object j for user i , $p_{i,j}$, corresponds to the encoding rate of the encoding algorithm applied. Throughout our investigation, we maintain a fixed frame rate (60fps in our experiments) and a consistent compression ratio. Notably, the frame rate remains constant throughout a gaming session, while

q_i may vary to accommodate different frame rate settings in various gaming sessions. Consequently, the video size before compression and the bitrate typically exhibit a linear relationship. Thus, the compressed data size of object j for user i is calculated as $l_{i,j} \cdot s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}$, and the available bandwidth for object j of user i is denoted as $l_{i,j} \cdot \mu$. This concept of superficial area aids in understanding the visible surfaces and their impact on data processing and transmission within the virtual environment. In the process of rendering the object, the transmission time can be determined by dividing the data size by the available bandwidth, as expressed by the following constraint:

$$\frac{l_{i,j} \cdot s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{l_{i,j} \mu} = \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (4)$$

Propagation Time: In mobile VR gaming latency, understanding propagation time is crucial, as it encompasses the transmission duration discussed earlier. Propagation time primarily depends on the transmission medium between the edge and the mobile device. Denoted as $\lambda_{i,d}$, the propagation time from location d , $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, to user i is of utmost importance. To ensure precise display of each object at a specific location, the propagation time for object j of user i is expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} \cdot x_{i,j,d}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (5)$$

where, $x_{i,j,d}$ might represent a binary variable associated with the propagation of uplink data for object j of user i .

Transmission Delay: Considering the preceding discussion, we can model the transmission delay for object j of user i , encompassing scenarios where the object is rendered locally, as follows:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} \cdot x_{i,j,d} + \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (6)$$

3.6 End-to-End Delay Constraint

Suppose τ represents the maximum tolerable end-to-end (E2E) delay, commonly set to 50 ms for VR to ensure a high-quality user experience in terms of QoE, Quality of Perception (QoP), and Quality of Demand (QoD). Given that all objects can render and transmit simultaneously, a user's E2E delay is determined by the maximum delay among all objects associated with that user. The overall end-to-end latency model comprises rendering and encoding delays, along with transmission and reception delays. Considering the mobile device as the rendering and encoding entity, the latency model. Therefore, the E2E delay constraint can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d} + \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} \cdot x_{i,j,d} + \\
& \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,2} \cdot \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu} \leq \tau, \\
& \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i,
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where we introduce a second dilation factor $\alpha_{d,2}$, emphasizing the critical importance of understanding the linear relationship between computation speed and workload for deciphering the performance dynamics of VR systems, especially in managing intricate virtual environments with fluctuating numbers of objects or elements requiring real-time processing.

3.7 Bandwidth Modeling Constraint

The capacity of the edge network is constrained due to its limited bandwidth. Given that the edge server is positioned at the initial network gateway for end users, the bottleneck within the edge network could stem from either the outgoing bandwidth at the edge server or the link bandwidth connecting the edge and the local mobile device. This bandwidth limitation affects data flow in both directions. Let's denote B_d , where $d \in \mathcal{D}$, as the outgoing bandwidth of edge d . Similarly, let $b_{d,i}$, with $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $d \in \mathcal{D}$, represent the respective link bandwidths between edge d and user i . Consequently, the channel's bandwidth constraint begins with the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq B_d, \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \tag{8}$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq b_{d,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \tag{9}$$

where the expression $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d}$ denotes the aggregate bandwidth requirements of all objects originating from each user on edge d .

4 Problem Formulation

In the previous section, we conceptualized the optimization objective as meeting visual requirements to accommodate a range of user interests while considering constraints such as delay, bandwidth, and placement within the model. Consequently, the problem involves incorporating delay constraints (7) and bandwidth constraints (8) and (9), along with binary constraints referred to as 'placement constraints' (1), which dictate the positioning of tasks or services within the infrastructure. As quadratic-constrained

problems often do not include equation constraints, it becomes essential to convert these equation constraints into inequalities to enable the attainment of solutions.

As each variable $x_{i,j,d}$ takes values in the set $\{0,1\}$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, and $d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, the summation $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ should result in a value within the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, D\}$, where D represents the size of set \mathcal{D} . Consequently, the equation $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1$ is equivalent to the inequality constraints $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1$ and $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \neq 0$. On the contrary, when $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 0$, it signifies that object j of user i is not rendered anywhere, resulting in the minimal visual QoE for object j of user i (i.e., the visual QoE is 0). Therefore, the equation constraint $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1$ can be replaced with the inequality constraint $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1$. Additionally, by incorporating $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ into the objective function and maximizing it, the sum of the placement decisions automatically avoids being 0. Therefore, the placement constraint is assured within the framework of an inequality.

To refine the algorithmic framework, we employ a transformation for all variables to 0-1 indicator variables. Specifically, we substitute each rendering level selection variable $l_{i,j} \in \mathcal{L}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$ with a set of rendering level indicator variables $l_{i,j,\psi} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, $\forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}$.

Here ψ indicates the rendering level, and $l_{i,j,\psi}$ signifies whether object j of user i is rendered at level ψ . Each rendering level ψ can be viewed as a factor that scales the importance or significance of the rendering status $l_{i,j,\psi}$ in the overall rendering process. As each object is rendered with precisely one rendering level, $\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} = 1$. To maximize the visual Quality of Experience (QoE), it follows that $l_{i,j,\psi}$ cannot all be 0. Therefore, we converted the equation constraint $\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} = 1$ to the inequality constraint $\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \leq 1$.

As a result, we define the QoE-oriented VR game service within a distributed edge network as:

$$\max. \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} \cdot \lambda \cdot \sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \cdot \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d} + \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d} \\ & + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,2} \cdot \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu} \leq \tau, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i,$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot x_{i,j,d} \cdot \left(\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \right) \leq B_d, \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mu \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \left(\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \right) \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq b_{d,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} &\leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \\
x_{i,j,d} &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}, \\
l_{i,j,\psi} &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}.
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The aim of addressing Problem (10) - (15) is to maximize the overall visual QoE for all users, while adhering to constraints related to E2E delay, object placement, and bandwidth. In contrast to prior studies, which primarily focused on meeting delay requirements in distributed mobile edge VR gaming [31–33], our approach stands out by considering a holistic QoE that incorporates both delay and visual considerations. The problem involves two types of variables: object placement variables ($x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$) and rendering level selection variables ($l_{i,j,\psi} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}$).

Analyzing Problem (10), it becomes evident that the objective function and Constraints (11), (12) and (13) all involve the multiplication of two distinct variable types. Consequently, the nature of the problem is identified as a Mixed-Integer Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Programming (MIQCQP) problem with 0-1 integer variables.

Convergence Performance: The inherent non-convexity of the general MIQCQP problem precludes the application of conventional methods reliant on strong convergence properties. However, an alternative avenue emerges through the utilization of the weak convergence property. This property stipulates that if an algorithm converges for the non-convex problem, it will converge to a Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) point. Moreover, as demonstrated, the MIQCQP problem can be readily reformulated as a QP problem for solution, highlighting a pivotal link between MIQCQP and QP. By iteratively updating the primal and dual variables, the algorithm converges to a KKT point, as demonstrated through the derivation of the KKT conditions. As the iteration index approaches infinity, both the primal and dual variables converge, ultimately satisfying the KKT conditions. This convergence property provides theoretical support for the reliability of the algorithm in finding meaningful solutions to the non-convex MIQCQP problem, showcasing the algorithm’s ability to navigate the complexities of non-convex optimization challenges and converge to KKT points, which represent critical points of the optimization problem. The proof of weak convergence in Appendix A supports the algorithm’s reliability in solving the non-convex MIQCQP problem.

Building on the optimization framework established in the *Problem Formulation* section, we now shift focus to a critical element of this framework: the Quality of Experience (QoE) weight formulation. The QoE in virtual reality (VR) applications is significantly shaped by the prioritization of different object types during user interaction. These interactions require a structured approach to allocate weights that accurately reflect their relative importance. By adhering to user-object interaction proportions and maintaining normalization, the QoE weight formulation provides a critical foundation for optimizing user satisfaction across diverse VR scenarios. The following section presents a systematic framework for computing the visual QoE weights $w_{i,j}$, incorporating dynamic adjustments and advanced optimization techniques to enhance user-centric VR experiences.

4.1 Framework for QoE Weight Formulation

The formulation of $w_{i,j}$, the QoE weights for VR object types, involves a systematic process that incorporates symbolic generalization, dynamic modeling, and optimization techniques. The motivations behind each step are discussed below.

4.1.1 Relative Importance Definition as a Symbolic Generalization

Motivation: In VR environments, object importance varies significantly depending on user perception, interaction context, and application goals. To model these differences effectively, it is necessary to represent object importance in a flexible and adaptable manner. Static weight assignments fail to capture the variability across applications or users, necessitating a symbolic generalization.

Formulation: The relative importance r_i of object type i is defined symbolically as:

$$r_i = k \cdot (\alpha - i),$$

where:

- $\alpha = c + 1$ represents the starting importance for the most significant object type,
- i is the object index, ranging from 1 to n ,
- k ensures normalization.

This generalization allows α to be adjusted dynamically, enabling the framework to adapt to diverse scenarios. For example, setting $\alpha = 5$ yields the widely used 4:3:2:1 ratio for object importance.

4.1.2 Normalization and Computation of QoE Weights

Motivation: To ensure fair and consistent representation of object importance across all object types, the weights must satisfy the normalization constraint $\sum w_{i,j} = 1$. This ensures that the weight distribution aligns with the relative significance of each object while maintaining a bounded total.

Formulation: The weights are computed as:

$$w_{i,j} = \frac{r_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i},$$

where the denominator normalizes the relative importance values. Expanding the summation term:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n r_i = k \cdot \left(n\alpha - \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \right),$$

the scaling factor k is derived as:

$$k = \frac{1}{n\alpha - \frac{n(n+1)}{2}}.$$

Significance: This step ensures that the QoE weights are not arbitrarily large or small and remain meaningful across applications, particularly when distributed among multiple users.

4.1.3 Dynamic QoE Modeling through Matrix Representation

Motivation: In realistic VR applications, interactions between users and objects are influenced by dynamic conditions such as user feedback, network variability, or environmental changes. A static representation of weights cannot account for these fluctuations. To address this, a matrix representation is employed to capture the dependencies and variances among object types.

Formulation: The relative importance vector \mathbf{r} is represented as:

$$\mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ \vdots \\ r_n \end{bmatrix}.$$

The QoE weight distribution is expressed dynamically as:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{r},$$

where \mathbf{D} is a diagonal scaling matrix reflecting dynamic adjustments:

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n).$$

Significance: The matrix-based approach introduces flexibility and scalability, enabling the model to incorporate dynamic user behavior and contextual changes.

4.1.4 Optimization with Eigenvalue Analysis

Motivation: User-object interactions often exhibit correlations and variances that influence QoE. For example, visually prominent objects might dominate user attention, while others have less impact. To capture these interaction patterns, eigenvalue decomposition is applied.

Formulation: The covariance matrix \mathbf{A} represents the interaction structure among object types. Eigenvalue decomposition:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T,$$

is performed, and the optimized weights are computed as:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{opt}} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}^T\mathbf{r}.$$

Significance: This step ensures that the weight distribution reflects real-world interaction patterns. Higher eigenvalues amplify the importance of certain object types, aligning the weights with the system's natural dynamics.

4.1.5 Constrained Optimization with Lagrange Multipliers

Motivation: In VR applications, weights must often satisfy additional constraints, such as ensuring total system resources are efficiently allocated or meeting specific network bandwidth limitations. The Lagrange multiplier method is employed to enforce these constraints while optimizing weights.

Formulation: The constrained optimization problem is defined as:

$$L = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{w} + \lambda \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_{i,j} \right),$$

where λ is the Lagrange multiplier. Solving:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = 0,$$

yields the optimal weights \mathbf{w}^* , which satisfy both the objective function and the normalization constraint.

5 Reinforcement Learning for QoE Optimization

In the context of optimizing Quality of Experience (QoE) in Virtual Reality (VR) applications, Q-Learning emerges as a robust reinforcement learning (RL) approach that effectively integrates optimal parameters derived from Mixed Integer Quadratically Constrained Programming (MIQCP). As a model-free algorithm, Q-Learning facilitates direct learning from environmental interactions without requiring a pre-defined model of system dynamics. This characteristic is particularly advantageous in complex optimization scenarios characterized by non-linear relationships among variables.

By incorporating weights, such as those derived from Eigenvalue or Lagrange Multiplier adjustments, into the state representation, the Q-Learning agent can make informed decisions to enhance QoE. These weights adaptively influence the reward signal and the exploration process, enabling real-time strategy adjustments based on historical data and evolving operational conditions. The Q-Learning update rule is given by:

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha [R(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s_{t+1}, a') - Q(s_t, a_t)], \quad (16)$$

where α is the learning rate, γ is the discount factor, and $R(s_t, a_t)$ is the immediate reward.

5.1 Reinforcement Learning Framework

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is formally modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), represented by the tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, P, R, \gamma)$, where:

- \mathcal{S} : A finite set of states representing the environment.

- \mathcal{A} : A finite set of actions available to the agent.
- $P(s'|s, a)$: Transition probability function, describing the probability of moving to state s' given state s and action a .
- $R(s, a)$: Reward function, assigning a scalar reward to each state-action pair.
- $\gamma \in [0, 1)$: Discount factor, balancing immediate versus long-term rewards.

The goal of RL is to determine an optimal policy π^* that maximizes the expected cumulative reward, or return:

$$G_t = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k R(s_{t+k}, a_{t+k}) \mid s_t = s \right]. \quad (17)$$

5.2 Bellman Optimality and Value Functions

The value function $V^\pi(s)$ represents the expected return starting in state s under policy π :

$$V^\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_\pi [G_t \mid s_t = s]. \quad (18)$$

The action-value function $Q^\pi(s, a)$ extends this concept to include action a :

$$Q^\pi(s, a) = R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) V^\pi(s'). \quad (19)$$

For the optimal policy π^* , the Bellman optimality equation is:

$$V^*(s) = \max_a \left[R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) V^*(s') \right]. \quad (20)$$

Similarly, the optimal action-value function satisfies:

$$Q^*(s, a) = R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) \max_{a'} Q^*(s', a'). \quad (21)$$

5.3 Application to QoE Optimization

By leveraging the theoretical foundations of RL and its practical integration with MIQCP, this approach provides a comprehensive framework for enhancing QoE in VR environments. The exploration mechanisms of Q-Learning enable efficient investigation of weight configurations, while its convergence guarantees ensure that, over time, the agent learns effective strategies to maximize user satisfaction.

The pseudocode for the workflow combining QoE optimization, weight selection, and reinforcement learning is shown in Algorithm 1. This algorithm demonstrates how these three components are integrated to optimize QoE while incorporating adaptive decision-making through reinforcement learning.

Algorithm 1 QoE Optimization, Weight Selection, and RL

Require: Users \mathcal{I} , objects \mathcal{J} , devices \mathcal{D} , latency threshold τ , bandwidth limits B_d , device capacities b_d , weights w_i , rendering levels $l_{i,j,d}$, placement decisions $x_{i,j,d}$.

Ensure: Optimal rendering levels $l_{i,j,d}^*$, placement decisions $x_{i,j,d}^*$, selected weights w_{selected} , RL-based policy $\pi^*(s)$.

- 1: **Step 1: Optimization with MIQCP**
- 2: Define the objective function to maximize QoE:

$$\max. \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} w_i \cdot \lambda \cdot \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} l_{i,j,d}^* \cdot x_{i,j,d}^*$$

- 3: Subject to constraints for latency, bandwidth, device capacities, and placement.
- 4: Solve the MIQCP problem using an optimization solver (e.g., Gurobi, CPLEX).
- 5: Extract optimal rendering levels $l_{i,j,d}^*$ and placement decisions $x_{i,j,d}^*$.
- 6: **Step 2: Weight Selection**
- 7: Choose a weighting method:

- **Default weights:** $w_{\text{default}} = \sum_{r=4}^1 [4, 3, 2, 1]$
- **Eigenvalue-based weights:** $w_{\text{eigen}} = \lambda U^T w_{\text{default}}$
- **Lagrange multiplier weights:** Optimize $\mathcal{L}(w, \lambda)$ via $\mathcal{L} = \lambda \cdot (1 - \sum w_i)$

- 8: **Step 3: Reinforcement Learning**
- 9: Initialize RL parameters: state space \mathcal{S} , action space \mathcal{A} , learning rate α , discount factor γ , exploration rate ϵ .
- 10: **for** each episode $t = 1, 2, \dots, M$ **do**
- 11: Initialize state s_t
- 12: Select action a_t using ϵ -greedy policy:

- With probability $1 - \epsilon$, take $a_t = \arg \max Q(s_t, a)$
- With probability ϵ , take a random action.

- 13: Apply action a_t , observe reward $R(s_t, a_t)$ and transition to s_{t+1}
- 14: Update Q -values:

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha [R(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s_{t+1}, a') - Q(s_t, a_t)]$$

- 15: **end for**
 - 16: Extract the optimal policy $\pi^*(s) = \arg \max Q(s, a)$.
-

6 Results

In this section, we present the results of our comprehensive analysis on the factors influencing QoE in VR gaming environments. We explore three key aspects: α_1 , α_2 , and τ , which represent critical parameters affecting the performance and user satisfaction in VR gaming systems. Subsequently, we investigate the relationship between the number of users and the Mbps throughput, providing insights into the scalability and network requirements necessary to support optimal VR experiences. Additionally, we

present the visual ratio of the QoE weights in Figure 5, offering insights into the prioritization of various QoE metrics and their significance in enhancing overall gaming immersion.

Fig. 3 3D Plot of τ vs. α_1 and α_2

6.1 Dilation Factor ($\alpha_{1\vee 2}$) and Max. Tolerable E2E delay (τ)

In the context of the VR system, the dilation factors $\alpha_1 \vee \alpha_2$ play pivotal roles in shaping the temporal and spatial characteristics of data processing and transmission, directly impacting the E2E delay. These factors represent the degree of expansion applied to different components within the system, influencing the speed and efficiency of data handling.

As we see in Figure 3, α_1 and α_2 increase, indicating greater levels of dilation, the system may require additional processing time or bandwidth to handle the expanded data streams effectively. Consequently, the maximum tolerable E2E delay τ tends to increase linearly with the dilation factors.

This observed linear relationship underscores the inherent trade-offs between processing complexity, spatial resolution, and E2E latency within the VR environment. While higher dilation factors may enhance image quality or spatial detail, they also introduce additional processing overhead and potential delays in delivering content to the user.

Optimizing the dilation factors involves striking a balance between achieving the desired visual fidelity and maintaining acceptable levels of E2E delay. By understanding the linear relationship between dilation factors and E2E delay, system designers can make informed decisions to fine-tune system parameters and enhance the overall user experience in the VR environment

Fig. 4 Bandwidth demand vs number of users.

6.2 Number of Users vs Mbps

The Figure 4 depicts results where the bandwidth available to users ranges from 10 Mbps through 90 Mbps. The x-axis represents the number of users, ranging from 1 to 10, while the y-axis indicates resulting bandwidth values ranging from approximately 2 Mbps to 153 Mbps. The data was transformed into a cubic format to model the relationship between user count and bandwidth demand due to their ability to accurately capture nonlinear behavior in the data. The bars points highlight the increasing demands on network resources as the user count rises, crucial for effective network planning and resource management to ensure optimal performance and Quality of Service (QoS). Interestingly, the analysis suggests a somewhat linear increase in bandwidth demand as user count grows, reflecting practical implications despite the underlying nature of the data.

This analysis of bandwidth allocation underscores the critical role of Quality of QoS considerations in network planning and resource management for VR environments. While bandwidth allocation is essential for supporting immersive VR experiences, E2E delay constraints also play a pivotal role in ensuring optimal user satisfaction. E2E delay constraints, represented by the maximum tolerable delay denoted as τ , impose significant limitations on system performance. They encompass various latency factors, including rendering, encoding, transmission, and reception delays. Our study integrates these constraints into the analysis to maintain seamless VR experiences and uphold stringent QoS standards.

The introduction of the dilation factor, $\alpha_{d,1}$ and $\alpha_{d,2}$, emphasizes the importance of understanding the linear relationship between computation speed and workload in VR systems. This factor further underscores the need for efficient resource allocation and management to mitigate delays and optimize system performance. The increasing demands on network resources, as depicted by the results, highlight the necessity for effective network planning and resource management strategies. By addressing bandwidth allocation and E2E delay constraints, organizations can enhance overall performance and quality of service in VR environments, thereby improving user satisfaction and immersive experiences (QoE).

Fig. 5 Comparison of QoE Weight Adjustment Strategies: Normalized weight distributions across four QoE levels are shown for default weights (blue), Lagrange multiplier-adjusted weights (red), and eigenvalue-adjusted weights (yellow). Default weights heavily prioritize the first level, while Lagrange and eigenvalue adjustments provide more balanced and dynamic distributions across all levels.

6.3 Visual QoE Weight Distribution Analysis

Figure 5 presents a comparative analysis of visual Quality of Experience (QoE) weight distribution across four levels under three different weight adjustment strategies: default weights, Lagrange multiplier-adjusted weights, and eigenvalue-adjusted weights.

The default weights (blue bars) exhibit a clear bias toward the first level, with approximately 40% of the total normalized weight assigned to it. This prioritization diminishes significantly across the second, third, and fourth levels, indicating that the default configuration emphasizes the initial QoE level at the expense of deeper levels. This approach, while simple, does not account for constraints such as bandwidth limitations or the nuanced dynamics of user-object interactions, often resulting in suboptimal resource utilization.

In contrast, the Lagrange multiplier-adjusted weights (red bars) provide a more balanced distribution. This method ensures that weights satisfy critical resource constraints, such as normalization and bandwidth limits, while maximizing the overall QoE. The first level still receives the highest proportion, but subsequent levels are comparatively more balanced. By aligning resource usage with QoE priorities, the Lagrange method achieves better overall efficiency, ensuring that limited resources are distributed effectively across all levels.

The eigenvalue-adjusted weights (yellow bars) exhibit a distinctly different distribution, with the first level receiving a substantially reduced share of the total weight compared to the other strategies. The weights for the second, third, and fourth levels are correspondingly higher, reflecting a strategic shift toward equalizing QoE contributions across all levels. This adjustment is particularly advantageous in scenarios where higher-level experiences play a critical role in user satisfaction. The eigenvalue analysis leverages correlations and variances in user-object interactions, allowing for a weight distribution that dynamically adapts to system conditions and optimizes resource use in real-time.

These advanced methods outperform the default configuration in multiple dimensions. While the default weights may suffice for applications prioritizing immediate QoE at a single level, the Lagrange multiplier and eigenvalue approaches enable dynamic adaptability, better resource allocation, and long-term QoE optimization. By effectively balancing competing priorities and constraints, these strategies ensure efficient use of limited resources while maximizing user satisfaction across all levels.

6.4 RL Average Reward Analysis with Weight Strategies

The Figure 6 shows the results of an RL experiment that compares the average rewards obtained under three different weight adjustment strategies over the course of 100 episodes. The y-axis represents the average reward, while the x-axis denotes the episode number.

The performance of the RL agent using default weights (blue line) serves as the baseline. Without any weight adjustment, the average reward remains consistently negative, fluctuating between -50 and -10 throughout the 100 episodes. This indicates that the agent struggles to learn effectively or achieve positive rewards under the

Fig. 6 Average Reward: This figure compares RL performance across 100 episodes for default weights (blue), eigenvalue-adjusted weights (red), and Lagrange multiplier-adjusted weights (green). Default weights show high variability and lower rewards, while tailored methods achieve consistent improvements with higher stabilized rewards.

default configuration, highlighting the need for more sophisticated weight optimization techniques.

In contrast, the use of eigenvalue-adjusted weights (red line) demonstrates rapid improvement in performance within the first 10 episodes. The average reward quickly surpasses zero and stabilizes at consistently positive values after approximately 15 episodes. This approach outperforms the default weights significantly, indicating its effectiveness in optimizing the learning process and enabling the RL agent to achieve superior results.

Similarly, the strategy employing Lagrange multiplier-adjusted weights (green line) shows rapid performance improvement, achieving positive rewards after about 10 episodes. While slightly trailing the eigenvalue-adjusted weights in the initial episodes, it eventually converges to comparable performance by the 50th episode. This indicates that both weight adjustment techniques are robust and effective, although the eigenvalue-based approach shows a slight advantage in the early stages of learning.

These findings underscore the critical role of weight optimization in reinforcement learning. The comparison highlights the substantial gains that can be achieved by

incorporating advanced techniques such as eigenvalue adjustments and Lagrange multipliers into the weight design process. Both methods significantly outperform the default weights, validating their utility in enhancing the agent’s ability to learn and accumulate rewards in structured environments. Moreover, the convergence of the adjusted weight strategies with consistently high reward levels demonstrates their robustness and stability.

This highlights the importance of tailored weight optimization techniques in reinforcement learning. The results suggest that further exploration of these methods, including potential combinations or applications to more complex RL tasks, could yield even greater improvements in agent performance.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we analyzed the relationship between user demands and bandwidth allocation, emphasizing the increasing strain on network resources and the necessity of maintaining stringent QoS standards for seamless VR experiences. Our work extended this analysis by integrating multiple QoE weight adjustment strategies, including default, Lagrange multiplier, and eigenvalue-based methods. These approaches revealed opportunities for optimizing resource allocation and improving visual QoE distribution among object types. Additionally, we addressed the constraints posed by limited edge network bandwidth, highlighting challenges such as bottlenecks in outgoing server bandwidth and link capacity between edge servers and mobile devices. By leveraging RL, we demonstrated dynamic resource management that adapts to real-time network and user conditions, achieving significant improvements in QoE and resource efficiency. Our findings underscore the importance of combining advanced optimization techniques and RL frameworks to enhance mobile edge VR gaming experiences. This comprehensive approach addresses latency concerns, optimizes visual quality, and ensures high QoE across distributed networks. These contributions advance the state-of-the-art in delivering QoE-centric services, bridging theoretical models and practical implementations for scalable VR applications.

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Appendix A Proof of Theorem 1

Proof: The MIQCQP problem can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_0^T \mathbf{x} + c_0 \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_s^T \mathbf{x} + c_s \leq 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \end{aligned} \tag{A1}$$

where the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ is a quadratic function of \mathbf{x} with the coefficient matrix \mathbf{A}_0 and the linear term \mathbf{b}_0 , along with a constant term c_0 . The constraints are quadratic inequality constraints, each with its own coefficient matrix \mathbf{A}_s , linear term \mathbf{b}_s , and constant term c_s . These constraints are imposed $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, which represents the indices of the constraints. By embedding all the inequality constraints and

range constraints within the objective function, we can observe that \mathbf{y} and $\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_m$ effectively represent the variables of the optimization problem in (10) to (15).

The corresponding algorithm iteration is described as follows:

Updating \mathbf{y}^{k+1} :

$$\mathbf{y}^{k+1} = (\mathbf{A}_0 + m\rho\mathbf{I})^{-1} [\rho(\mathbf{z}_s^k + \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) - \mathbf{b}_0], \quad (\text{A2})$$

where (A2) updates \mathbf{y}^{k+1} in the optimization algorithm. It calculates the new value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous values of \mathbf{z}_s^k and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$, using the matrices \mathbf{A}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 . This update ensures that \mathbf{y}^{k+1} satisfies the optimization problem, considering the influence of the dual variables $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$ and the objective function represented by \mathbf{A}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 .

Updating \mathbf{z}^{k+1} :

$$\mathbf{z}^{k+1} = \operatorname{argmax} \|\mathbf{z}_s - \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k\|^2 \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\text{s.t.: } \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_s^T \mathbf{x} + c_s \leq 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where this step involves updating \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} in the algorithm. \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} is optimized to minimize the squared Euclidean distance between \mathbf{z}_s , \mathbf{y}^{k+1} , and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$, while ensuring compliance with the quadratic inequality constraints for all s .

Updating $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1}, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

where (A5) describes the update process for each $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ in the algorithm. It calculates the new value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ by adding the difference between \mathbf{y}^{k+1} and \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} to the previous value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. This update is applied to $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.

Therefore, $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + m\rho \mathbf{y}^{k+1} = \rho(\mathbf{z}_s^k + \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) - \mathbf{b}_0, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\mathbf{z}^{k+1} = \operatorname{argmax} \|\mathbf{z}_s - \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k\|^2, \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\exists \eta_s^{k+1} \geq 0, \text{ s.t.: } \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \eta_s^{k+1} (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} + \mathbf{b}_s) = 0, \quad (\text{A8})$$

where (A6) computes the updated value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous values of \mathbf{z}_s^k and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. In (A7) is determined \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} by maximizing the squared distance between \mathbf{z}_s , \mathbf{y}^{k+1} , and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. The introduction of Lagrange multipliers η_s^{k+1} ensures that the updated $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ values adhere to the constraints, as specified in (A8). These equations collectively drive the iterative update process of the optimization algorithm, aiming for convergence towards a solution that simultaneously satisfies the optimization problem and its constraints.

Since

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1}, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (\text{A9})$$

and

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\mathbf{z}_s^k - \mathbf{y}^k) = 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (\text{A10})$$

we have,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) = 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (\text{A11})$$

where (A9) represents the iterative update for the dual variable $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$ in the optimization algorithm. It computes the new value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ by adding the difference between \mathbf{y}^{k+1} and \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} to the previous value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. This update is applied to $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, ensuring that each dual variable is appropriately adjusted based on the current values of \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{z} . The limit expression in (A10) indicates that as the iteration index k approaches infinity, the difference between \mathbf{z}_s^k and \mathbf{y}^k tends to zero $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. This suggests that the sequences \mathbf{z}_s^k and \mathbf{y}^k converge to the same value as k becomes very large, implying potential convergence of the optimization algorithm. Similarly, the limit expression (A11) indicates that as k tends to infinity, the difference between consecutive iterations of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$ converges to zero $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. This suggests that the sequence $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$ converges to a stable value as the algorithm progresses, potentially indicating convergence of the dual variables.

Therefore, when $k \rightarrow +\infty$,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + m\rho \mathbf{y}^{k+1} = \rho [\mathbf{y}^k - \eta_s^{k+1} (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + \mathbf{b}_s)] - \mathbf{b}_0, \quad (\text{A12})$$

where (A12) represents an update step in the optimization algorithm. It calculates the new value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous value of \mathbf{y}^k , along with the Lagrange multiplier η_s^{k+1} , and the matrices \mathbf{A}_s and \mathbf{b}_s . With (A12), it ensures that \mathbf{y}^{k+1} satisfies the optimization problem while considering the impact of the constraint terms represented by \mathbf{A}_s and \mathbf{b}_s .

By further assuming,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\mathbf{y}_s^{k+1} - \mathbf{y}_s^k) = 0,$$

we have,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^* + \mathbf{b}_0 + \sum_{s=1}^m \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^* (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{y}^* + \mathbf{b}_s) = 0, \quad (\text{A13})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^* = \rho \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ and $k \rightarrow +\infty$ are the corresponding dual variables. Note that (A13) is the KKT condition of (A1). Therefore, any limit point of $\{\mathbf{y}^k\}$ is a KKT point. ■

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